

PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF FORMATION OF MUSICAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN STUDENTS.

SamSU, Faculty of Sports and Arts

Lecturer at the Department of Art History

Samatova Dilnoza Salaidinovna

Omankulova Shohida Nematillo qiz

teacher of music education department of the Uzbek-Finnish Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of Art History

Annotation: *The article describes in detail the pedagogical basis for the development of executive skills in students. The article also aims to reveal the pedagogical aspects of the development of musical performance skills of students studying in higher education in the field of music education.*

Keywords: *instrumental performance, students, teacher, performance status, curtain pressing, moans, right hand and left hand, musician, fingers location, performing arts; executive skills; education and upbringing, pedagogical content.*

The huge reforms being carried out in the new Uzbekistan, the radical changes in the system of higher education, which is the main link in the social sphere of society, serve to improve the education, creativity and content of education programs are being developed and implemented. The priorities of social, economic and cultural development of Uzbekistan include the formation of the education system, its content and essence on a new, national and modern basis. "As the head of our state said in his congratulatory speech to teachers and educators on the occasion of Teachers 'and Coaches' Day, science, education and upbringing are the cornerstone of development and the power that makes a country strong and a nation great."¹[1]. In this sense, one of the main tasks of the education system is to increase the interest of students in the field of music, which is one of the main means of education and the performance of musical instruments, and their desire to learn.

¹ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/talim-tarbiya-tizimi-taraqqiyotning-yangi-bosqichi-muhokama-qilindi>

The main executors of this task are the directions of music education of pedagogical higher educational institutions.

5111100 - "Music Education" prepares a future music teacher. The subject of "Instrumental Performance" plays a special role in equipping them with theoretical and pedagogical knowledge. The course of instrumental performance teaches students the development of instrumental performance skills and the factors influencing it, the pedagogical process and its essence, theoretical and practical knowledge of performance, the laws and principles of the performance process, the content of the work, performance methods. and the development of execution techniques.

The experience of pedagogical and scientific observations shows that testing the ability of those interested in playing musical instruments focuses on their musical hearing, melody memorization and method perception. This process is carried out in students who first entered music schools. . The fact that they can play on any instrument of their choice, that all aspects of it fit into that instrument, makes it easy and enjoyable for the teacher and the student to perform.

“Performance refers to how the whole body, head, arms, legs, and wind instruments are ready to breathe in order to hold, prepare, and play the instrument. The executive position includes the whole body, head, arms, legs, holding the instrument, and the position of the lips in the mouthpiece (ambushyur). Getting the performance right from the start is one of the most important tasks and the most important guarantee of achieving high performance results. The right hand plays an important role in making the sound by wearing a finger on the index finger of the tanbur. However, the left hand is at the forefront of cursing and moaning. The dutar is a scratching word that involves all the fingers of the right hand. In addition, the dutar beats are given in the form of a circle, and the dutar cover is given a manual method (dutar lazgis, double). The left hand is used to press the curtain and make a sound (under the double). Rubab and oud are played with a mezrob, which is a mediator. The mezrob is held between the thumb and forefinger of the right hand. Because the wires are paired, the vibration of the

words expands when the mezzobass is hit. The fingers of the left hand are used only to press the curtain. The placement of the fingers on the instrument should be based on their natural position. " [2]

Each teacher has a unique pedagogical approach to developing students' musical performance skills. There are also general pedagogical aspects to developing instrumental performance skills. Here are some of them:

- introduction to the musical work, the genre of the work, the tone of the work, its shape, parts and character, the traditions formed in the performance of the work.

- the student's performance temperament, attitude to the work.

- the style of the teacher in the study of a new work, the focus of the teacher and the student on the same goal.

the melody is defined, the main performance and artistic means are considered.

- the teacher explains the content and essence of the work.

- when working on the work, the development of the melody and the sentences, syllables, parts of the melody are clearly defined.

- the technically complex parts of the work are identified and studied individually with a note.

- critically evaluate their performance and gradually play the difficult parts.

- in-depth study and memorization of the work from an artistic point of view,

- to perform a common performance, in deep harmony with the narrator.

- the teacher should have a deep knowledge of the given work, to alleviate some of the complexities of the work.

As you know, any piece of music is a work of art. Performing it at the level of a work of art requires thorough knowledge, high skill and performance skills from the musician. As the teacher develops the student's performance skills, he or she should be able to develop a love for the instrument. To do this, from the very beginning it is necessary to include in the repertoire works that sound as good as possible, that the student likes, and that strengthen the desire to learn them. When working on a piece, it is important to ensure that each bar produces good sound

from the beginning, as the volume and quality of the musician is one of the main criteria for artistic expression of the performance. Artistic expression is important in the performance of Uzbek folk instruments. No matter how good a musician's performance technique may be, it will not make a good impression on the listener if it does not reveal the artistic features of the work. Such a work has a dry, lifeless, soulless appearance. To do this, the musician must be familiar with his instrument and master the expressive features of the bars, be able to use them as needed, as well as be able to create and control a clear melody. should be.

It is very difficult to master such skills and it takes some time. In practice, there are musicians who have a high level of performance technique but cannot feel the melody. As the teacher engages with the student, he or she should continuously nurture the student's delicate senses, such as the ability to feel and perceive music, in each session.

Each melody, each instrument has its own characteristics and capabilities. The colorful colors of the instruments allow them to play unique works. That's why every musician should know his instrument well.

From the dynamics of the melody to the use of each bar, all the methods of performance serve as a means of artistic expression, that is, the state of the word, the quality of the sound must be constantly monitored. Students need to be taught this from the very beginning. Good quality instruments play an important role in the smooth sound of a piece of music.

In the learning process, special attention should be paid to the development of the student's musical consciousness, memory and sense of rhythm, as well as the ability to hear, not only by studying the melodies of a particular curriculum or only exam papers. To do this, the teacher can take a creative approach to the lesson process, carefully observe the students and find different opportunities to achieve the goal. Here are some of them:

1. To teach the student to perform a work by the teacher, to analyze it together and to explain to the students the artistic aspects, to clarify the content,

that is, to adapt the music in the work to the student's worldview and feelings. figurative comparison of sentences.

2. Listening to the melodies on the magnetic tapes with the students, discussing and analyzing them, or explaining their differences, shortcomings and advantages by comparing 2-3 different performances of the same piece on the instrument.

3. Performing and listening to concerts within and outside the educational institution. After the concert, of course, the teacher analyzes the performance of the concert and shows the good performances to the students.

Performance skills also require very precise rhythm, especially in sentences that play a key role in the melody of the melody. It is also a form of artistic expression, which reveals the character of the melody.

Developing a clear rhythm is different for each student. Therefore, enumeration, piano accompaniment, use in various forms of ensemble performance (duet, trio, quartet), study of special melodies accompanied by a circle give good results. This is one of the factors that helps to develop students' performance skills.

The Tremolo bar is especially colorful. Moreover, in opening the character of this bar, not only the smooth movement of the right hand, but also the movements of the fingers of the left hand, their smooth transition or sliding from one curtain to another, as well as It is achieved by the ability to 'lqinlata.

In Uzbek music alone we can see several types of tremolo. If we see the continuity, enthusiasm and various rhythmic performances of the tremolo in the Bukhara-Samarkand direction, we can see some flat, clear-sounding tremols in the melodies on the Fergana-Tashkent route. . Due to the artistic nature of the composers' works, a gentle tremolo gives the impression of sadness, despair, and contemplation, while in another, the same tremolo gives the listener a feeling of calm and peace of mind. Of course, the skills of the performer have a special place in this.

In some works, where the composer does not have a clear character, there are ways to slow down the tempo of the musical sentences, to play them as if they are slowing down, or, conversely, to play them with an internal movement without accelerating the tempo, which requires sufficient skill from the performer. The implementation of such methods depends on how deeply the performer understands the artistic essence of the work and the formation of performance skills. This makes the melody sound more perfect and complete when performed by a musician accompanied by a piano, ensemble or orchestra.

In short, mastering the skills of performing Uzbek folk instruments, the ability to perform works with full artistic value requires a musician to work hard and research. To achieve this level, the student must not only master the skills of playing a musical instrument, that is, a professional instrument, but also have a musical mind that can understand and analyze the performance of works on Uzbek folk instruments. . This means being able to feel the music deeply.

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